

Research Paper

Teachers’ Classroom Management Skills as Correlates of Students’ Academic Achievement in Economics in Ika North-East Local Government Area of Delta State

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Abstract

This study examined teachers’ classroom management skills as correlates of students’ academic achievement in Economics in Ika North-East Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria. Four research questions and four corresponding hypotheses guided the study. A correlational research design was adopted for the investigation. The study population comprised Senior Secondary School Three (SS III) students in public secondary schools within the study area. Using a purposive sampling technique, a sample of 120 Economics students was selected. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire, which was subjected to pilot testing to establish its reliability. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach’s Alpha, yielding a coefficient of 0.74, indicating satisfactory internal consistency. Descriptive statistics, particularly the mean, were used to answer the research questions, while the hypotheses were tested using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient at the 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed significant positive relationships between teachers’ classroom management skills, teachers’ use of instructional materials, teachers’ disciplinary skills, and students’ academic achievement in Economics. The study concludes that effective classroom management practices contribute substantially to improved academic performance among secondary school students. It therefore recommends that Economics teachers should consistently apply effective classroom management strategies, utilize appropriate instructional materials, and maintain positive disciplinary practices to create a conducive learning environment capable of enhancing students’ academic achievement.

Keywords: Classroom Management Skills, Academic Achievement, Economics Education, Instructional Materials, Discipline, Secondary School Students

1. Introduction

Economics is a social science concerned with the allocation and utilization of scarce resources to satisfy unlimited human wants. It examines the behaviour of individuals, households, firms, and governments in making decisions regarding the production, distribution, and consumption of goods and services. As noted by Ajabor (2015), Economics is an essential subject for all citizens because it equips learners with the knowledge and skills required to understand the functioning of economic systems and make rational decisions in both personal and public life.

The Economics curriculum for senior secondary schools in West Africa is therefore designed to expose students to fundamental economic principles, concepts, and analytical tools that will enable them to understand national and international economic issues, appreciate the structure of the economy, and develop informed decision-making skills.

The successful realization of these educational objectives depends largely on the quality of teaching and the effectiveness of classroom management. Among the various factors that influence students' academic achievement, the teacher remains one of the most significant determinants. Teachers are responsible not only for delivering instructional content but also for creating a classroom environment that promotes effective learning, discipline, motivation, and active student participation. The quality of classroom instruction and students' learning outcomes are therefore closely associated with teachers' professional competence and classroom management skills.

Recognizing the central role of teachers in educational development, the *National Policy on Education* (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013) emphasizes that no educational system can rise above the quality of its teachers. The policy identifies several objectives of teacher education, including the production of highly motivated, competent, and professionally committed teachers capable of promoting creativity, critical thinking, and effective learning. It further advocates continuous professional development to enable teachers to adapt to changing educational environments and improve instructional effectiveness.

Within the context of Economics education, classroom management extends beyond maintaining order and discipline. It encompasses the planning and organization of instructional activities, effective utilization of instructional materials, management of classroom interactions, motivation of learners, and the creation of an environment that supports meaningful learning. According to Mezieobi (2009), effective classroom management involves organizing learning experiences, coordinating instructional resources, evaluating learning outcomes, and facilitating positive behavioural changes among learners. Economics classrooms are expected to encourage active participation, discussion, and problem-solving, thereby enabling students to develop analytical and critical thinking skills necessary for understanding economic concepts. Similarly, Thebereme (2013) argued that when teachers fail to actively engage students during classroom instruction, learners tend to become passive, less attentive, and less motivated to learn.

Despite the importance of effective classroom management, concerns over the declining academic performance of secondary school students in Nigeria continue to attract considerable attention from educators, policymakers, parents, and other stakeholders. Persistent poor performance in public examinations has generated widespread concern regarding the quality of teaching and learning in secondary schools, particularly in subjects such as Economics. Several studies have suggested that students' academic performance is influenced by teachers' subject matter knowledge, instructional competence, communication skills, classroom discipline, and

the effective use of instructional materials. Etuk et al. (2013) observed that students often evaluate their teachers based on these professional attributes, all of which contribute significantly to classroom effectiveness and learning outcomes.

Although previous studies have examined factors affecting students' academic achievement, relatively few have specifically investigated the relationship between teachers' classroom management skills and students' performance in Economics within secondary schools in Delta State. Given the importance of classroom management in facilitating effective teaching and learning, there is a need to provide empirical evidence on how teachers' management practices influence students' academic achievement in Economics. It is against this background that this study examines teachers' classroom management skills as correlates of students' academic achievement in Economics in Ika North-East Local Government Area of Delta State.

2. Statement of the Problem

An effective Economics classroom is expected to provide a conducive environment that promotes active learning, meaningful interaction, and the development of critical thinking skills among students. Classroom instruction should be learner-centred, allowing teachers and students to engage collaboratively in the teaching–learning process. Achieving these goals depends largely on teachers' classroom management skills, including effective lesson preparation, organization of instructional activities, appropriate use of instructional materials, classroom discipline, and the selection of suitable teaching strategies.

Despite the importance of these classroom management practices, students' academic performance in Economics in many secondary schools has remained unsatisfactory. In many instances, teachers experience difficulties in maintaining an effective learning environment, while inappropriate classroom management practices may discourage students' participation, reduce their interest in learning, and contribute to poor academic achievement. Attempts to maintain classroom order through ineffective disciplinary practices may further create an unconducive learning atmosphere, leading to lackadaisical attitudes toward learning and reduced motivation among students.

Although several factors have been identified as determinants of students' academic achievement, there is limited empirical evidence on the extent to which teachers' classroom management skills influence students' performance in Economics, particularly in Ika North-East Local Government Area of Delta State. This gap in the literature necessitates an empirical investigation into the relationship between teachers' classroom management practices and students' academic achievement. It is against this background that this study examines teachers' classroom management skills as correlates of students' academic achievement in Economics in Ika North-East Local Government Area of Delta State.

3. Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study is to examine the relationship between teachers' classroom management skills and students' academic achievement in Economics in Ika North-East Local Government Area of Delta State.

Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. examine the relationship between teachers' classroom management skills and students' academic achievement in Economics;
2. determine the relationship between teachers' use of instructional materials and students' academic achievement in Economics; and
3. examine the relationship between teachers' disciplinary skills and students' academic achievement in Economics.

4. Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between teachers' classroom management skills and students' academic achievement in Economics?
2. What is the relationship between teachers' use of instructional materials and students' academic achievement in Economics?
3. What is the relationship between teachers' disciplinary skills and students' academic achievement in Economics?

5. Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at the 0.05 level of significance:

- H_{01} : There is no statistically significant relationship between teachers' classroom management skills and students' academic achievement in Economics.
- H_{02} : There is no statistically significant relationship between teachers' use of instructional materials and students' academic achievement in Economics.
- H_{03} : There is no statistically significant relationship between teachers' disciplinary skills and students' academic achievement in Economics.

6. Literature Review

6.1. Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the *Classroom Management Theory* propounded by Jacob Kounin (1970). The theory posits that effective classroom management practices create an orderly, engaging, and supportive learning environment that enhances students' participation and academic performance. According to Kounin, teachers who effectively organize classroom activities, maintain discipline, monitor students' behaviour, and sustain learners' attention are more likely to achieve positive instructional outcomes. The theory emphasizes that successful classroom management is preventive rather than corrective, requiring teachers to anticipate potential disruptions while maintaining continuous student engagement throughout the instructional process.

The Classroom Management Theory is particularly relevant to this study because it explains how teachers' classroom management behaviours influence students' engagement, motivation, and ultimately their academic achievement. Effective management of classroom activities, instructional resources, and student behaviour provides a conducive atmosphere for meaningful learning, thereby improving students' performance in Economics.

6.2. Concept of Classroom Management

Classroom management refers to the strategies and practices employed by teachers to establish and maintain an effective learning environment that promotes students' academic success and positive behaviour. It involves organizing classroom activities, managing instructional time, maintaining discipline, utilizing appropriate teaching resources, and fostering positive teacher-student relationships. David (2016) described classroom management as the creation of a positive classroom environment through appropriate behavioural standards, effective instructional practices, and continuous student engagement to facilitate quality education.

Similarly, Wisetrinthong et al. (2012) defined classroom management as the process of improving the teaching and learning environment through effective interaction between teachers and students, proper supervision, motivation, and classroom control. According to the authors, effective classroom management facilitates cooperation among learners and teachers, enhances instructional effectiveness, and ultimately improves students' academic performance.

Pederson-Seelye (2011) argued that effective classroom management procedures promote independent learning by creating productive, orderly, and pleasant classroom environments where students can achieve academic success. Likewise, Omomia and Omomia (2014) maintained that effective classroom organization is reflected in teacher behaviours that maximize students' involvement in classroom activities while minimizing disruptive behaviours that interfere with learning and instructional time.

Instructional materials constitute another important component of classroom management. Effective utilization of instructional materials enhances students' understanding of concepts by making abstract ideas more concrete and stimulating learners' interest. Igu et al. (2014), in their study on the effects of instructional materials on students' achievement in Economics, reported that students taught using appropriate instructional materials performed significantly better than those taught without such materials. Similarly, Abdu-Raheem (2011) identified the inadequate provision and utilization of instructional materials as major contributors to ineffective teaching and poor academic performance in schools. Ekpo (2004) also emphasized that instructional aids facilitate learning by appealing to multiple senses and enhancing students' comprehension and retention of instructional content.

Another important dimension of classroom management is classroom discipline. Effective disciplinary practices create an atmosphere conducive to learning by minimizing disruptive behaviours and encouraging responsible conduct among students. Gawe et al. (2001) argued that discipline and academic performance are closely related, noting that effective classroom discipline promotes cooperative learning and improves educational outcomes. While some scholars attribute students' poor academic performance to high levels of indiscipline within schools, others contend that effective classroom management can substantially reduce behavioural problems and improve learning outcomes. Supporting this position, Matsoga (2003) reported widespread incidents of violence and misconduct in secondary schools and concluded that ineffective disciplinary practices negatively affect students' academic achievement.

Overall, the reviewed literature suggests that classroom management skills—including effective classroom organization, appropriate use of instructional materials, and sound disciplinary practices—play significant roles in promoting students' engagement and enhancing academic achievement. However, empirical evidence regarding these relationships within the context of Economics education in Ika North-East Local Government Area of Delta State remains limited. This study therefore seeks to fill this gap by examining the relationship between teachers' classroom management skills and students' academic achievement in Economics.

7. Results

7.1. Research Question 1

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between teachers' classroom management skills and students' academic achievement in Economics?

Table 1 presents the respondents' mean ratings on the relationship between teachers' classroom management skills and students' academic achievement in Economics. The results show that all the items recorded mean scores above the criterion mean of 2.50, indicating that respondents agreed with all the statements.

Table 1. Mean Ratings on the Relationship Between Teachers' Classroom Management Skills and Students' Academic Achievement in Economics.

S/N	Items	Mean (\bar{x})	Decision
1	The ability of teachers to organize the classroom and effectively manage students' behaviour is critical to achieving positive educational outcomes.	3.30	Accepted
2	Teachers' management of homework and assignments has a positive influence on students' academic achievement.	3.33	Accepted
3	Effective classroom management creates and maintains a learning environment that supports instruction and enhances students' academic achievement.	3.26	Accepted
4	Comprehensive and well-articulated classroom rules and procedures promote effective classroom behaviour.	3.49	Accepted
5	Teachers employ strategies that instil confidence in students through appropriate guidance and direction.	3.43	Accepted

Source: Field Survey (2026).

Specifically, respondents agreed that teachers' ability to organize the classroom and manage students' behaviour is essential for achieving positive educational outcomes ($\bar{x} = 3.30$). They also agreed that effective management of homework and assignments contributes positively to students' academic achievement ($\bar{x} = 3.33$). Furthermore, respondents affirmed that effective classroom management creates and maintains a conducive learning environment that supports instruction and enhances students' academic achievement ($\bar{x} = 3.26$).

The findings further revealed agreement that clearly defined classroom rules and procedures promote appropriate classroom behaviour ($\bar{x} = 3.49$), while teachers' use of strategies that build students' confidence through guidance and direction also contributes positively to learning ($\bar{x} = 3.43$).

Overall, the findings suggest that respondents perceive teachers' classroom management skills as playing a significant role in enhancing students' academic achievement in Economics.

7.2. Research Question 2

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between teachers' use of instructional materials and students' academic achievement in Economics?

Table 2 presents the respondents' mean ratings on the relationship between teachers' use of instructional materials and students' academic achievement in Economics. The findings reveal that all the items recorded mean scores above the criterion mean of 2.50, indicating that respondents agreed with all the statements relating to the effective use of instructional materials.

Specifically, respondents agreed that adequate instructional materials facilitate effective teaching and learning ($\bar{x} = 3.53$). They also agreed that inadequate instructional materials

Table 2. Mean Ratings on the Relationship Between Teachers' Use of Instructional Materials and Students' Academic Achievement in Economics.

S/N	Items	Mean (\bar{x})	Decision
1	Adequate instructional materials enable effective teaching and learning.	3.53	Accepted
2	Inadequate instructional materials constitute one of the major causes of poor academic achievement.	3.50	Accepted
3	Instructional materials used during teaching should be clearly visible to every student in the classroom.	3.44	Accepted
4	Adequate instructional materials help students develop the appropriate sequence for carrying out learning activities.	3.47	Accepted
5	Adequate instructional materials promote strategies that facilitate the integration of technology into the teaching and learning process.	3.51	Accepted

Source: Field Survey (2026).

constitute one of the major factors responsible for poor academic achievement among students ($\bar{x} = 3.50$). Furthermore, respondents indicated that instructional materials should be clearly visible to all students during classroom instruction to enhance understanding ($\bar{x} = 3.44$).

The findings further showed that adequate instructional materials help students develop the appropriate sequence for carrying out learning activities ($\bar{x} = 3.47$). In addition, respondents agreed that adequate instructional materials promote instructional strategies that facilitate the integration of technology into the teaching and learning process ($\bar{x} = 3.51$).

Overall, the results suggest that the effective use of instructional materials contributes positively to students' academic achievement in Economics.

7.3. Research Question 3

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between teachers' disciplinary skills and students' academic achievement in Economics?

Table 3 presents the respondents' mean ratings on the relationship between teachers' disciplinary skills and students' academic achievement in Economics. The findings indicate that all the items recorded mean scores above the criterion mean of 2.50, showing that respondents agreed with all the statements relating to teachers' disciplinary skills.

Specifically, respondents agreed that strictly enforcing classroom rules is necessary for controlling students' behaviour ($\bar{x} = 3.49$). They also agreed that clearly communicating behavioural standards and academic expectations to students promotes discipline within the classroom ($\bar{x} = 3.57$). Furthermore, respondents indicated that students should not leave the classroom without obtaining the teacher's permission ($\bar{x} = 3.52$).

The findings also revealed agreement that effective teaching skills play a central role in establishing and maintaining classroom discipline ($\bar{x} = 3.51$). Similarly, respondents agreed that

Table 3. Mean Ratings on the Relationship Between Teachers' Disciplinary Skills and Students' Academic Achievement in Economics.

S/N	Items	Mean (\bar{x})	Decision
1	Strictly enforced classroom rules should be adopted to control students' behaviour.	3.49	Accepted
2	The standards for students' behaviour and academic expectations should be clearly communicated to ensure discipline.	3.57	Accepted
3	Students should not leave the classroom without the teacher's permission.	3.52	Accepted
4	Effective teaching skills are fundamental to establishing and maintaining classroom discipline.	3.51	Accepted
5	Creating and maintaining classroom order promotes quality teaching and effective learning.	3.52	Accepted

Source: Field Survey (2026).

creating and maintaining an orderly classroom environment enhances the quality of teaching and learning ($\bar{x} = 3.52$).

Overall, the results suggest that teachers' disciplinary skills contribute positively to students' academic achievement in Economics by promoting an orderly and conducive learning environment.

7.4. Hypothesis 1

H_{01} : There is no statistically significant relationship between teachers' classroom management skills and students' academic achievement in Economics.

Table 4. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Between Teachers' Classroom Management Skills and Students' Academic Achievement in Economics.

Variables	N	r	p-value (2-tailed)	Decision
Teachers' Classroom Management Skills	120	0.643	0.042	Reject H_{01}
Students' Academic Achievement in Economics	120			

Source: Field Survey (2026).

Table 4 presents the Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis examining the relationship between teachers' classroom management skills and students' academic achievement in Economics. The analysis yielded a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.643$, indicating a moderate positive relationship between the two variables. The corresponding probability value was $p = 0.042$, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance.

Since the calculated p -value (0.042) is less than the significance level (0.05), the null hypothesis (H_{01}) is rejected. This implies that there is a statistically significant positive relationship

between teachers' classroom management skills and students' academic achievement in Economics. The finding suggests that improvements in teachers' classroom management skills are associated with improved academic performance among students in Economics.

7.5. Hypothesis 2

H_{02} : There is no statistically significant relationship between teachers' use of instructional materials and students' academic achievement in Economics.

Table 5. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Between Teachers' Use of Instructional Materials and Students' Academic Achievement in Economics.

Variables	<i>N</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i> -value (2-tailed)	Decision
Teachers' Use of Instructional Materials	120	0.744	0.019	Reject H_{02}
Students' Academic Achievement in Economics	120			

Source: Field Survey (2026).

Table 5 presents the Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis examining the relationship between teachers' use of instructional materials and students' academic achievement in Economics. The analysis produced a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.744$, indicating a strong positive relationship between the two variables. The corresponding probability value was $p = 0.019$, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance.

Since the calculated p -value (0.019) is less than the significance level (0.05), the null hypothesis (H_{02}) is rejected. The result indicates that there is a statistically significant positive relationship between teachers' use of instructional materials and students' academic achievement in Economics. This finding suggests that the effective use of instructional materials enhances students' understanding of Economics concepts and contributes positively to improved academic performance.

7.6. Hypothesis 3

H_{03} : There is no statistically significant relationship between teachers' disciplinary skills and students' academic achievement in Economics.

Table 6. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Between Teachers' Disciplinary Skills and Students' Academic Achievement in Economics.

Variables	<i>N</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i> -value (2-tailed)	Decision
Teachers' Disciplinary Skills	120	0.810	0.022	Reject H_{03}
Students' Academic Achievement in Economics	120			

Source: Field Survey (2026).

Table 6 presents the Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis examining the relationship between teachers' disciplinary skills and students' academic achievement in Economics. The analysis yielded a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.810$, indicating a strong positive relationship between teachers' disciplinary skills and students' academic achievement. The corresponding probability value was $p = 0.022$, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance.

Since the calculated p -value (0.022) is less than the significance level (0.05), the null hypothesis (H_{03}) is rejected. The result indicates that there is a statistically significant positive relationship between teachers' disciplinary skills and students' academic achievement in Economics. This finding suggests that effective classroom discipline contributes to the creation of an orderly learning environment that enhances students' academic performance in Economics.

8. Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study revealed a significant positive relationship between teachers' classroom management skills and students' academic achievement in Economics. The descriptive analysis showed that respondents agreed that teachers' ability to organize the classroom, manage students' behaviour effectively, supervise homework and assignments, establish clear classroom rules, and provide appropriate guidance contributes to improved academic performance. The hypothesis testing further confirmed this relationship, as the Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis revealed a statistically significant positive relationship between teachers' classroom management skills and students' academic achievement in Economics. This finding implies that effective classroom management enhances students' engagement, promotes a conducive learning environment, and improves learning outcomes in Economics.

The result is consistent with the Classroom Management Theory of Kounin (1970), which emphasizes that effective classroom organization and management foster greater student engagement and academic success. The finding also agrees with Pederson-Seelye (2011), who maintained that effective classroom management promotes independent learning and creates productive, orderly, and pleasant learning environments that enhance students' academic achievement. Similarly, Omomia and Omomia (2014) argued that effective classroom organization increases students' involvement in classroom activities while minimizing disruptive behaviours that interfere with teaching and learning. Collectively, these studies support the view that teachers who effectively organize instructional activities, establish clear classroom procedures, and maintain positive classroom environments contribute significantly to students' academic achievement.

The study also found a significant positive relationship between teachers' use of instructional materials and students' academic achievement in Economics. Respondents agreed that adequate instructional materials facilitate effective teaching and learning, improve students' understanding of concepts, encourage logical learning sequences, and support the integration of technology into

classroom instruction. The correlation analysis further established that teachers' use of instructional materials is significantly related to students' academic achievement in Economics. This suggests that the effective utilization of instructional materials enhances students' comprehension of Economics concepts and improves their overall academic performance.

This finding corroborates the study conducted by Igu et al. (2014), who reported that students taught with appropriate instructional materials performed significantly better than those taught without such materials. Likewise, Abdu-Raheem (2011) observed that the inadequate provision and utilization of instructional materials constitute major factors responsible for poor academic performance among students. Ekpo (2004) further emphasized that instructional materials enhance learning by stimulating learners' sensory organs, thereby improving understanding, retention, and academic achievement. The present finding therefore reinforces the importance of adequate instructional resources in facilitating effective Economics instruction.

Furthermore, the findings revealed a significant positive relationship between teachers' disciplinary skills and students' academic achievement in Economics. Respondents agreed that effective classroom discipline requires clearly defined classroom rules, explicit behavioural expectations, proper supervision of students, and the maintenance of order during classroom instruction. The hypothesis testing also confirmed that teachers' disciplinary skills have a statistically significant relationship with students' academic achievement in Economics. This indicates that effective disciplinary practices contribute to the establishment of an orderly classroom environment that supports quality teaching and learning.

The finding is consistent with the views of Gawe et al. (2001), who argued that classroom discipline is fundamental to effective teaching and improved academic performance. Similarly, Matsoga (2003) reported that indiscipline, including bullying, truancy, vandalism, substance abuse, lateness, and classroom misconduct, negatively affects teaching and learning in secondary schools. The present study therefore suggests that teachers who effectively manage classroom discipline are better positioned to create learning environments that promote students' concentration, participation, and academic success in Economics.

Overall, the findings demonstrate that teachers' classroom management skills, effective use of instructional materials, and sound disciplinary practices are important determinants of students' academic achievement in Economics. These findings further support the proposition that creating a well-organized, resourceful, and disciplined classroom environment enhances students' learning experiences and contributes positively to improved academic outcomes.

9. Conclusion and Recommendations

9.1. Conclusion

This study examined the relationship between teachers' classroom management skills and students' academic achievement in Economics in Ika North-East Local Government Area of Delta State. Based on the findings, it was concluded that teachers' classroom management skills have a significant positive relationship with students' academic achievement in Economics. Effective classroom organization, appropriate management of students' behaviour, and the establishment of a conducive learning environment were found to contribute positively to students' academic performance.

The study further established that teachers' effective use of instructional materials is significantly related to students' academic achievement in Economics. The availability and appropriate utilization of instructional resources enhance teaching effectiveness, improve students' understanding of Economics concepts, and facilitate meaningful learning experiences.

Finally, the study concluded that teachers' disciplinary skills also have a significant positive relationship with students' academic achievement in Economics. Effective classroom discipline promotes orderliness, encourages positive learning behaviours, minimizes classroom distractions, and creates an environment conducive to effective teaching and learning. Overall, the findings demonstrate that teachers' classroom management practices constitute important determinants of students' academic achievement in Economics.

9.2. Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Economics teachers should consistently apply effective classroom management strategies and make appropriate use of instructional materials during the teaching–learning process in order to improve students' academic achievement.
2. Teachers should continually strengthen their classroom disciplinary skills through regular professional development programmes and training on effective classroom management practices to promote a conducive learning environment.
3. School administrators should provide adequate supervision and support to ensure that teachers effectively implement appropriate classroom management techniques that enhance students' participation and academic performance.
4. Governments at all levels, in collaboration with relevant educational stakeholders, should provide adequate funding for the procurement of instructional materials, teaching facilities, and continuous professional development programmes for Economics teachers to improve the quality of instruction and students' academic achievement.

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